

THE REPRESENTATION AND FUNCTION OF NATURE IN "DEMON COPPERHEAD" BY BARBARA KINGSOLVER

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Abstract

The article explores how the theme of nature and its function is represented in Barbara Kingsolver's "Demon Copperhead", drawing on the theoretical framework of ecocriticism. The forms of nature depicted in the novel complete both performative and aesthetic functions. Through close analysis of key extracts from the novel, the paper reveals the link between ecocritical theory and Kingsolver's social criticism.

Keywords: ecocriticism, Demon Copperhead, landscape, aesthetic function, symbolism, imagery, performative function.

Introduction

Barbara Kingsolver's "Demon Copperhead" is a Pulitzer winning novel which narrates the story of an orphan boy trying to survive in rural Appalachian society. The story is told from the protagonist's point of view and includes his journey from his early childhood to his young adult years. Kingsolver touches upon some dire social problems of late 20th and early 21st century that are bothering rural Appalachia such as opioid epidemic and systematic failure.

The narrative structure of the novel is of anti-bildungsroman pattern; however, the novel shows the essential features of eco-poetic writing. Although it is not one of the main themes of the work, nature plays an important role in setting the background of the narrative and characterising the protagonist. Moreover, the natural environment of Appalachian Mountains acts as the symbol of Demon's spiritual and moral anchor. Barbara Kingsolver interweaves vivid imagery in the novel with professional mastery, which contributes to realise the aesthetic function of nature.

The analysis of "Demon Copperhead" from ecocritical point of view provides a solid basis for reflecting on how theory and literature intersects. The novel is examined through the framework of ecocriticism, focusing on the forms and functions of nature as they align with author's philosophy and ethics.

The close textual reading of "Demon Copperhead" reveals that the novel contains the following forms of nature: landscape, animals, climate and seasons. From an ecocritical perspective, author's association of landscape, or space if we put it in general, is analysed by Lawrence Buell in his work *"The future of environmental criticism: Environmental crisis and literary imagination"*. Buell differentiates the terms space and place, defining the space as the which "connotes geographical or topographical abstraction" and quoting Carter: the place is a "space to which meaning has been ascribed" [Carter, Donald, & Squires, 1993, as cited in Buell, 2005:63]. In his effort to highlight the representation of place-attachment in literature, Buell refers to Barbara Kingsolver's essay "The memory place". In her essay, Kingsolver describes her visit to her birthplace in Appalachia with her little daughter; however, it is not merely nostalgia she intends to depict, but her ecological concern for Horse Lick Creek. She manages to

interweave ecological message regarding the place skilfully through her rhetorical question by the end of the essay: *"Who will love the imperfect lands, the fragments of backyard desert paradise, the creek that runs between farms?"* [Kingsolver, 2002, as cited in Buell, 2005:74]"

Buell draws attention to another aspect of eco-criticism in his book *"The environmental imagination: Thoreau, nature writing, and the formation of American culture"*, the personification of nature. He analyses Thoreau's works and singles out sense of belonging in particular stating Thoreau's "contributions to this literature of belonging, however, was to widen irretrievably the split between the communal bond to place and the individual bond" [Buell, 1995:210]. *This bond is reflected in Demon's longing for Appalachian Mountains during the three years he spends outside the county, as he constantly reminisces about them.*

Greg Garrard offers another important angle of ecocriticism focusing on animals in fiction in his work "Ecocriticism". What bears a strong relevance to the ecocritical analysis of "Demon Copperhead" is the discussion of wild animals predominantly within documentaries and partly, novels [Garrard,2004:136]. He focuses on extinction of species such as birds and the spiritual bond between animals and people. "Demon Copperhead" can exemplify both subjects of discussion through mentioning *"bird less birdhouses"* and the times when *"dogs had foxes or bears to chase up a tree"*. Regarding the spiritual connection between animals and human beings, the nickname "Copperhead" given to Demon symbolises his bond with the specie. Throughout the novel, people prejudice the valley, calling it the home of copperheads yet no actual snake appears till the end of the narrative—mirroring how Demon himself, as an orphan from rural area, is frequently overlooked and underestimated.

In the further analysis of "Demon Copperhead", several forms of nature appear: landscape, animals, plants and seasons. Barbara Kingsolver describes mainly Appalachian rural scenery such as mountains and valleys. Demon narrates that the place he lives is *"Dead in the heart of Lee County, between the Ruelynn coal camp and a settlement people call Right Poor"* [Kingsolver,2022:9]. Similarly, the animals and plants not only reflect the moral and spiritual connection of the protagonist with his birthplace, but also demonstrate writer's concern about ecological issues. The snake Copperhead symbolises Demon's confused identity and foxes, bears as well as birds mentioned in the novel subtly hint at the extinction of species. The tobacco fields in which Demon works likewise draw the attention of the readers to the problem of unjust exploitation and degradation of land. Furthermore, the author skilfully uses the alteration of seasons in sync with character's mood and changes in his inner world.

Nature performs both performative and aesthetic functions in the novel as it forms the setting, characterises the protagonist, influences the plot and ensures the artistic depth of the narration. For instance, the snake Copperhead and the Devil's Bathtub alter the sequence of events as they are both connected to the death of Demon's father – Damon Woodall as well as Fast Forward (Sterling Ford) and Hammer Kelley. As for the aesthetic function, the description of Devil's Bathtub from Demon's point of view highlights how skilfully Kingsolver uses imagery and symbolism:

"The falls were a tame trickle and the pool itself a deep, easy blue. Taking art classes on repeat, you learn a lot about color, but I can't explain that blue. You see it in photos of icy lands. Peacock blue in the deep center, shading out to clear on the pebbly edges. The water was dimply and alive on top, perfectly still underneath. My eye kept going back to the turquoise middle [Kingsolver, 2022:485]"

Having discussed "Demon Copperhead", it is possible to infer that the author's general attitude to nature is scientific, ecological, critical and spiritual at the same time. *Linda Wagner-Martin states that Barbara Kingsolver's works are studied from ecological point of view several times in the Preface of her book "Barbara Kingsolver's world: Nature, art, and the twenty-first century".* However, she offers fused discussion of "Kingsolver's use of different lines of scientifically based knowledge with readings of her 14 books" [Wagner-Martin, 2019:10] and concludes that the author was able to blend science, morality, spirituality and ecological message successfully. What is more, we can single out her recurring motifs such as fertility, seasons, wilderness, animals and rootedness based on the aforementioned resources.

Conclusion

At the end of this exploration, it is evident that Barbara Kingsolver is able to incorporate ecological message with moral and spiritual meaning in her novels. The close reading of her novel "Demon Copperhead" proves that nature in her writing, although it is not the main theme but a background, can perform the role of an agent, influencing the events, and aesthetic core of the narrative. Moreover, she succeeds in subtly drawing the attention of the reader to the ecological issues of Appalachia such as lands exploited for unjust mining purposes without exaggeration. The readers will feel the deeper ecological concern through anti-bildungsroman narrative embedded with protagonist's struggle for search of identity.

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